

Study of Rainfall Pattern & Irrigation Water Utilization for various crops of Rapar Taluka of Kachchh

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ABSTRACT

The rainfall in Kachchh District is very scanty and irregular and the district has very few rainy days. The average annual rainfall in the district is between 300 mm to 400 mm. The number of rainy days varies between 14 days to 17 days.

The Rapar taluka is located on the eastern side of Kachchh district. The region mostly consists of sandy clay soil. It has two medium irrigation schemes Suvi and Fatehgadh of the 20 medium irrigation schemes of Kachchh region.

Rapar taluka has a geographical area of 302769 hectares of which 130805 hectares is used for cultivation of various crops. The main crops include Cotton, G. Nut, Wheat, Isabgul, Juwar, Bajari, Fodder etc. The utilization of water for these crops varies in Rabi, Kharif and Hot water cultivation.

Through this paper it is attempted to study the Rainfall Pattern and its effect on the cropping pattern and water utilised from medium irrigation schemes for various crops of the taluka for a period of 10 years.

ABOUT THE STUDY AREA

Kachchh is an ancient land possessed of great antiquity, which takes its name from its geographical characteristics and topographical features resembling a tortoise. This crescent shaped region forms part of the northwest Gujarat.

The district stretches roughly from 22°44'11" (approx.) to 24°41'25" (approx.) north latitudes and 68°09'46" (approx.) and 71°54'47" (approx.) east longitudes. It is bounded on the north and north-west by Sindh (Pakistan), on the north-east by Rajasthan, on the east by the districts of Banaskantha and Mehsana, on the south-east by Surendranagar district, on the south by the Gulf of Kachchh and the Rajkot district and on the south-west and west by the Arabian Sea.

The Rapar taluka is located on the 23° 32' north latitude and 70° 4' east longitude. It lies on the eastern part of the Kachchh district. The district is roughly divided into four parts i.e Kachchh mainland, Wagad region, Island belt comprising of four islands in the desert region and the Rann portion. Rapar taluka is a part of the Wagad region of Kachchh.

Figure 1 Location map for Kachchh District and Rapar taluka

Rainfall

The normal rainfall for Kachchh district ranges between 300 to 400 mm. The district receives an average annual rainfall of 356 mm (for study period of 1878 to 2007), which is erratic and depends on the strength of the summer monsoon. It ranges from 342.2mm at Bhuj to 451.9mm at Naliya. It varies from 407.5 mm (16.5”) at Mandvi on the southern coast to 249.4 mm (9.81”) at Lakhpat on the northwest coast. The variation in the annual rainfall from the year to year is very large. The coefficient of variation in rainfall is more than 70% in the western part but decreases towards the southwest. The monsoon rains usually set in by the third week of June in the coastal belt and withdraws by the end of September. The maximum rainfall takes place during the month of July and very less rain occurs during the month of August and September. Most of annual rainfall in the district is received during the southwest monsoon season, July being the rainiest month. Rainfall of about 178 to 468 mm in a single day has also been recorded at many stations.

The average annual rainfall for Rapar taluka is 365 mm. Table 1 shows the annual rainfall for Rapar taluka as well as Kachchh district for the period 1878 to 2007. During period 1878 to 2007 the highest annual rainfall amounting to 996 mm for Kachchh district occurred in the year 1959 and 1235 mm for Rapar taluka in the same year. Between the years 1878 to 2007 the district experienced drought (received less than 200 mm rainfall) for the years 1899, 1901, 1904, 1911, 1915, 1918, 1923, 1924, 1925, 1939, 1942, 1960, 1963, 1968,1969, 1972,1973,1974 & 1987. The rainfall value very high (more than 500 mm) for the years 1878, 1881, 1884, 1897, 1908, 1912, 1913, 1917, 1926, 1944, 1059, 1979, 1994 & 2003. Figure 2 shows the bar graphs and 3 year and 5 year moving mean graphs for Rapar taluka as well as Kachchh district.

Figure 2. Comparison of Average Annual Rainfall of Rapar Taluka & Kachchh District

Table 1 Comparison of Average Annual Rainfall for Rapar Taluka and Kachchh District (Values in mm)

Year	Rainfall for Rapar Taluka in mm	Rainfall for Kachchh District in mm	3 yr moving mean for Rapar taluka	3 yr moving mean for Kachchh district	5 yr moving mean for Rapar taluka	5 yr moving mean for Kachchh District
1878	594	791				
1879	308	254	480	460		
1880	537	336	532	421	527	487
1881	750	673	578	464	518	420
1882	448	382	581	503	584	533
1883	545	455	545	552	542	518
1884	642	818	504	512	450	475
1885	324	262	419	512	395	471
1886	291	456	263	360	326	449
1887	173	362	221	388	248	349
1888	201	346	209	342	224	342
1889	252	317	220	297	250	302
1890	205	228	292	267	347	330
1891	417	255	428	329	414	334
1892	661	504	538	374	553	440
1893	535	364	714	572	561	442
1894	946	847	575	485	586	496
1895	244	243	578	538	585	503
1896	544	523	482	435	559	493
1897	657	539	535	458	370	328
1898	403	312	354	291	414	352
1899	2	24	290	232	331	270
1900	465	362	198	166	269	216
1901	128	114	314	248	242	232
1902	349	269	248	259	267	247
1903	266	394	248	253	231	212
1904	128	95	225	227	303	288
1905	282	190	299	259	311	326
1906	487	492	387	379	350	327
1907	392	456	446	450	440	404
1908	459	403	478	446	441	454
1909	581	481	442	441	355	371
1910	284	439	308	332	376	388
1911	60	76	281	352	426	444
1912	498	541	422	433	395	422
1913	707	683	544	531	369	367
1914	426	369	429	406	425	431
1915	153	165	307	310	437	461
1916	342	396	351	418	318	344
1917	558	694	337	396	295	339
1918	110	97	327	377	341	365
1919	313	341	268	245	396	377
1920	381	296	437	364	337	287
1921	617	455	421	332	346	290
1922	265	245	345	271	322	262
1923	154	114	205	186	269	235
1924	195	199	154	159	264	318
1925	112	164	300	410	340	366
1926	594	868	450	505	361	389
1927	645	484	500	527	373	417
1928	263	230	386	350	400	447

1929	252	337	254	294	327	306
1930	246	316	243	273	265	290
1931	231	165	270	294	316	343
1932	332	402	361	354	375	350
1933	521	496	466	422	432	361
1934	546	369	532	413	430	391
1935	531	373	433	352	448	383
1936	223	315	391	350	390	335
1937	420	363	291	311	297	278
1938	231	254	244	234	237	251
1939	82	85	181	192	289	253
1940	231	235	265	216	231	222
1941	483	326	281	256	233	221
1942	128	208	283	261	360	328
1943	239	248	362	359	420	363
1944	719	620	497	427	373	349
1945	534	414	499	429	398	381
1946	243	254	344	345	387	352
1947	255	368	228	241	305	317
1948	185	103	249	306	234	313
1949	308	448	224	314	256	306
1950	181	392	280	354	275	308
1951	353	221	294	330	318	396
1952	349	377	367	380	377	384
1953	398	542	451	437	409	360
1954	606	392	448	400	392	399
1955	340	267	404	359	376	368
1956	267	419	292	303	383	344
1957	270	222	323	354	509	465
1958	432	421	646	546	471	439
1959	1235	996	606	518	501	499
1960	152	138	601	617	482	504
1961	418	718	247	368	415	442
1962	171	248	230	359	205	288
1963	102	110	152	194	232	318
1964	184	225	190	208	231	222
1965	285	290	294	251	291	327
1966	413	236	389	434	293	321
1967	469	775	332	364	264	290
1968	115	79	208	308	266	363
1969	40	69	149	268	231	371
1970	291	657	191	334	151	227
1971	240	276	199	329	195	238
1972	67	53	214	155	198	235
1973	335	137	153	81	326	174
1974	58	53	442	181	395	172
1975	932	353	524	223	526	223
1976	582	263	746	309	507	263
1977	724	310	515	303	649	411
1978	239	337	576	479	498	417
1979	766	790	395	505	465	449
1980	180	386	454	532	355	423
1981	416	419	257	329	377	432
1982	175	183	313	328	299	334
1983	348	381	300	288	300	299
1984	376	300	303	298	236	250
1985	185	212	218	229	204	218
1986	94	176	98	137	189	257

1987	16	22	128	258	187	280
1988	274	574	219	337	205	286
1989	368	414	305	411	213	270
1990	273	245	258	251	288	394
1991	134	93	266	328	287	302
1992	390	645	264	283	356	413
1993	268	111	457	576	344	411
1994	714	973	399	440	394	425
1995	215	236	437	457	481	411
1996	382	161	475	323	528	470
1997	828	573	571	380	430	329
1998	503	405	518	416	426	330
1999	223	269	307	305	420	372
2000	194	241	256	294	301	283
2001	352	372	259	247	336	348
2002	231	129	422	410	331	330
2003	682	728	370	346	391	341
2004	197	179	457	400	427	380
2005	491	294	407	347	486	463
2006	532	567	517	470	422	389
2007	529	548				

Source: Meteriological Department, Gandhinagar

Cropping Pattern

The average net area sown in Kachchh district is less than 15 percent of its total geographical area. The main crops in the district are pearl millet (bajra), sorghum (jowar), pulses (moong and moth), groundnut, wheat, oilseeds and cotton. Cultivation of crops such as rice, gram, tur, sugarcane, tobacco, chilli, onion, garlic etc is either totally absent or negligible due to inadequacy of rains and poor soils. Cereals account for about 23 % of the gross cropped area while cash crops cover about 34% area. Datepalm and mango are the major horticultural crops.

The normal crop growing period in the district varies from about 12 weeks around Bhuj to 15 weeks in Anjar-Kandla area. It usually commences in the first week of July and continues till the last week of September. It is usually 12 weeks at Rapar. The mean length of the growing season, which is 8 weeks, occurs when the annual rainfall is about 200mm at 68% probability level. This is adequate for major kharif pulses like green gram and moth. Among cereals, pearl millet (bajra) is more suitable than sorghum (jowar) due to higher water use efficiency of the former. They occupy 30% of the cultivated area in the district. The southern and eastern areas which have better soils and usually a slightly higher rainfall have larger area under cotton, which is an important cash crop of the district.

The probability of onset of normal (26th to 28th week) sowing rains (more than 20 mm per week) were about 35% at Rapar. The early sowing rains can commence in 33% of the years and the late sowing rains occur at 25% if the years.

Irrigation System

There are totally 20 medium irrigation schemes in Kachchh of which two medium irrigations schemes located in Rapar taluka. Most of the irrigation in the region is done using water supplied from these medium irrigation schemes and extraction of ground water. Suvi and Fatehgadh are the two medium irrigation schemes located in Rapar taluka. The details of the water utilized for both the Irrigation schemes is given in the table 2. The Figure 3 shows the comparison of rainfall at Rapar and the actual irrigation from the period 1982 to 2006.

Figure 3. Comparison of Average Annual Rainfall and Actual Irrigation

Table 2 Comparison of Average Annual Rainfall and Actual Irrigation

Year	Annual Rainfall at Rapar in mm	Actual Irrigation through Suvi in hectares	Actual Irrigation through Fatehgadh in hectares	Total Irrigation in hectares
1982	175	770.40	38.99	809.39
1983	348	402.45	53.65	456.10
1984	376	339.30	166.68	505.98
1985	185	369.75	170.46	540.21
1986	94	392.60	141.20	533.80
1987	16	116.54	41.95	158.49
1988	274	789.43	291.61	1081.04
1989	368	691.38	164.20	855.58
1990	273	148.85	477.94	626.79
1991	134	876.47	0.00	876.47
1992	390	0.00	508.00	508.00
1993	268	0.00	293.20	293.20
1994	714	339.10	311.68	650.78
1995	215	953.30	0.00	953.30
1996	382	778.30	502.26	1280.56
1997	828	1256.20	460.95	1717.15
1998	503	1086.69	381.60	1468.29
1999	223	950.35	330.25	1280.60
2000	194	432.30	155.52	587.82
2001	352	157.29	55.05	212.34
2002	231	754.89	264.22	1019.11
2003	682	1256.23	439.68	1695.91
2004	197	211.11	76.00	287.11
2005	491	165.65	56.00	221.65
2006	532	549.82	310.00	859.82

Source: Kachchh Irrigation Circle, Bhuj

Conclusions

For the study period of 1878 to 2007 for the rainfall pattern, for about 40% of the years, the rainfall value is much less than the average annual value of rainfall for Kachchh district as well as Rapar taluka thus indicating drought situation. For about 30% of the years, the rainfall value is much higher than the average annual value of rainfall thus indicating years of surplus rainfall. For rest of the 30% years, the values are almost near to the average annual rainfall value. However the proportionate value of rainfall at Rapar is slighter better as compared to that of Kachchh district.

Most of the years show more consumption of water for agriculture as compared to the proportion of annual rainfall values for Rapar taluka. This shows that there is use of ground water in significant quantity for the purpose of irrigation. Further, the region receives some water from the Sardar Sarovar Project (Narmada River) which has not been accounted for separately. Thus the area irrigated actually is much higher as compared to the area irrigated using water stored in both the irrigation schemes.

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